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CHILDREN'S LITERATURE: METHODOLOGIES USED BY ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF PRESIDENTE KENNEDY- ES

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this research was to identify the methodologies used by elementary school teachers in the municipal school system in the municipality of Presidente Kennedy-ES in their work involving children's literature. This is an exploratory study of a qualitative nature, carried out with seven elementary school teachers and a pedagogue from the São Salvador Municipal Primary School. Data was collected by means of an interview and the data was analyzed using content analysis. The results showed that the teachers understand the importance of children's literature and that they use various resources to develop it, being encouraged by the school's pedagogical team to use different strategies to develop the students. They also try to motivate the children and offer enjoyable activities that allow for greater participation and, consequently, better learning. It can therefore be concluded that there is an understanding on the part of the professionals that children's literature is an important element in the development of the learning process, as it stimulates motivation and strengthens reading comprehension. However, progress still needs to be made in the methodologies used, in order to offer students opportunities to make sense of texts and understand the potential of each mode of communication, in order to make choices that allow them to create and understand messages more fully.

Keywords: Teaching and learning. Children's literature. Methodologies.

INTRODUCTION

Children's literature is a broad category, ranging from picture books to young adult fiction, from texts four hundred years old to the latest publications, and is an attractive form of literacy and literary art that not only improves reading skills, but also develops critical and creative thinking skills.

The genre involves works including classics of world literature, picture books and easy-to-read stories written exclusively for children, as well as fairy tales, lullabies, fables, folk songs and other material transmitted mainly orally.

For Bakhtin (1992), because it is a motivating and challenging instrument, children's literature is capable of transforming the individual into an active subject, responsible for their learning, who knows how to understand the context in which they live and modify it according to their needs.

Students can learn to evaluate and analyze literature, as well as summarize and formulate hypotheses about the subject. Zilberman (2005) states that in the early years of schooling, for example, wordless picture books are excellent stimuli for oral and written language, and they can analyze the illustrations and develop their own dialogue for the story. This strengthens students' cognitive functions, as they are able to form opinions on their own and express themselves through language, summarizing the plot of a book without words.

Finally, children's literature is valuable because it is a timeless tradition, in which books are the main means of transmitting literary heritage from one generation to the next. Children are young for a period of time, so they must have access to a literary heritage, understanding that quality works have the great power to captivate audiences for many generations (HUNT, 2010).

According to Solé (1998), mastering reading is one of the greatest challenges facing schools, as it is an essential requirement for the autonomy of individuals in a literate society. Reading goes beyond deciphering symbols and involves understanding and constructing meanings about the text.

In this sense, it is necessary to reinforce the need for methodologies and resources for the use of

children's literature in the process of learning to read in the early grades, in order to move from instruction based on student skills, a traditional approach, to a more holistic instructional method that makes use of lessons that emphasize the integration of the four components of language arts: reading, writing, listening and speaking.

What can be seen is that literature, as well as all creative and questioning culture, is not being explored as it should be in schools. This study proposal aims to contribute to theoretical growth and to help teachers in the municipal school system develop applicable teaching strategies, given the lack of research in this area.

Thus, this topic was brought up because of the importance of developing children's language and reading skills in the early grades of elementary school. In this context, the aim of this study is to identify the methodologies used and the profile of teachers in the early grades of elementary school in the municipal school system of Presidente Kennedy-ES.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out using descriptive, exploratory, qualitative research. The locus of the research is the São Salvador Municipal School of Early Childhood Education and Elementary Education, located in the rural area of the municipality, in the community/neighborhood of São Salvador, in Presidente Kennedy/ES, serving students from the local community and surrounding areas in Early Childhood Education, Elementary Education and Youth and Adult Education (EJA).

The sample was non-probabilistic, using inclusion and exclusion criteria, and included teachers and pedagogues from grades 1 to 5. The inclusion criteria were being a teacher and/or pedagogue in the initial grades from the 1st to the 5th year of elementary school, and the exclusion criteria were teachers who were absent on the days the survey was carried out or who did not sign the informed consent form. After delimiting the sample according to these criteria, we arrived at a sample of seven teachers and one pedagogue, who are responsible for 134 students in the 1st to 5th grades of elementary school.

The data was collected through an interview, which sought to identify the methodologies used to use children's literature, in order to better understand the views of these subjects.

Data collection was only carried out after approval by the Research Ethics Committee, Opinion No. 4.560.405 and, due to the need for physical distancing imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic, it was carried out through the Zoom platform, in an online interaction, where the respondent was informed of the research objectives. The interviews were transcribed and the data was analyzed using Bardin's (2011) content analysis, following the pre-analysis stages, with an exhaustive reading of the interviews, coding and categorizing them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When analyzing the personal and professional identification of the teachers interviewed, two (33.3%) were male and four (66.7%) female. With regard to the year of schooling in which they work, two (33.3%) are 2nd year teachers; one (16.7%) is a 3rd year teacher; one (16.7%) is a 4th year teacher; and two (33.3%) are 5th year teachers.

The sample had one (16.7%) undergraduate degree and five (83.3%) postgraduate degrees. As for professional experience, two (33.3%) teachers have been working for less than 5 years, one (16.7%) has been working between five and 10 years and three (50%) have been working for more than 10 years.

The pedagogue taking part in the research has a postgraduate degree and has been working in the position for over 10 years. When asked if she had ever seen any students who had difficulty with language skills, reading and interpreting images and texts in children's books or textbooks, she replied in the affirmative.

When looking at the results obtained, it is possible to see that there is a predominance of women among those interviewed, showing that teaching is still a predominantly female field. The feminization of teaching is not only a historical process, but

fundamentally reproduces stereotypical models of femininity and masculinity, identifying women as carers and educators by nature, endowed with characteristics such as kindness, patience, understanding and the ability to generate a climate of joy and enthusiasm in the classroom. This construction of women as "beings for others" permeated the discourse of thinkers and educators and, as a consequence, triggered the feminization of teaching (FERREIRA, 2015).

It was also possible to observe that all the teachers are graduates, with a significant percentage of postgraduates, a situation that contributes to qualified work in the classroom. This situation differs from the national average, where, according to Hirata et al. (2019), in early childhood education and the first segment of primary education, there are no adequately trained teachers for around 80% of classes, a situation that is even worse in secondary education and the second segment of primary education.

As for the length of time they have been working, it can be seen that the teachers are experienced, most of them having been in the classroom for more than five years, which leads to greater knowledge about the processes of acquiring reading and the possible difficulties students may have, as well as methodologies to help them when they have difficulties.

Asked if they have taught or are teaching any students who have difficulties with language skills, reading and interpreting images and texts in children's books or textbooks, all the teachers and the pedagogical coordinator said yes.

Probably every classroom teacher has come across students who have some difficulty with their reading and writing skills, making it a challenge for many teachers. Understanding that the ultimate goal of reading should be comprehension so that the reader can reconstruct the writer's mental world, reading goes beyond deciphering codes. For skilled readers, this often seems very easy and comprehension flows naturally as they read.

However, this sense of ease is deceptive, as it belies the complexity of what is done while reading,

even when a text is simple and straightforward. A whole range of cognitive and linguistic operations are at play, from identifying individual words to making inferences about situations that are not fully described in the text. This complexity means that finding a simple answer to questions about “how reading comprehension develops” or “why it sometimes fails” quickly becomes a complex task (AMARILHA, 2013).

When asked if children’s literature contributes to children’s learning, the teachers and pedagogical coordinator said yes.

For Cavalcanti (2002), in order to form good readers, an essential situation in the various segments of children’s and adults’ lives, literature goes beyond support material, and is essential and should be worked on from the first years of schooling, stating that:

Reading has always represented one of the most significant links between human beings and the world. Reading reflects and makes us present in history. Man has always read the world. On the walls of caves or on computer devices, they reproduce their being in the world and recognize themselves as capable of representation. Certainly, reading is an existential commitment. When we say reading, we mean all forms of reading. By reading, we become more human and sensitive (CAVALCANTI, 2002, p. 13).

When asked if they tell stories to their students, all the teachers said yes. Regarding the main advantage of telling stories in the classroom, the answers are presented below.

“In my opinion, it will make learning easier because at the same time as the student listens, he also learns the pronunciations of the words [sic].”

“Because it stimulates the student’s thinking, imagination and creativity, as well as their interest in reading [sic].”

“It’s about awakening emotion, pleasure and critical thinking [sic] in the child.”

“As well as developing reading and writing, you contribute to each child’s writing repertoire [sic].”

“Yes. It contributes to personal and intellectual development, leading the child into the world

of reading and writing, providing for the child’s development and learning [sic].”

“The enchantment and involvement of the class with the storytelling, which mostly happens spontaneously [sic].”

“It helps in the development of writing and orality [sic].”

The way teachers present reading to their students, the concrete actions they use to develop it, their own attitude towards books, their consistency in carrying out activities that involve reading different types of texts and their own example and motivation, all lead students to adopt their own view of reading, which can be positive or negative, depending mainly on the teaching model they are faced with (SOARES, 2007).

Another important point that teachers must take into consideration, according to Cosson (2009), are the motivations and tastes of their students when it comes to reading, since the idea of reading is a pleasurable moment for the child, which is related to their interests, which causes satisfaction and responds to their own concerns, not leaving aside learning that is expected; in other words, the way the teacher carries out their pedagogical practice, the concrete actions they take in the classroom, makes the student build their own conceptions of the process and development of the reading process.

Storytelling is the transmission of events in words, images and sounds, often through improvisation or embellishment. According to Busatto (2008), educators have found that the arts can play an important role in a student’s academic success and emotional well-being.

When asked what teaching resources they use to tell stories, the answers are shown below.

“I usually use texts. As the 5th grade class is larger, my strategy is to let them read and after reading we ask the appropriate questions [sic].”

“Books, fan flowers, pictures, puppets, etc. [sic].”

“I usually use texts. As the 5th grade class is larger, my strategy is to let them read and after reading we ask the appropriate questions [sic].”

“Most of the time I read for pleasure, but

sometimes I use role-playing [sic].”

“The textbook, handouts, movies, activities, exercises, illustrations, CDS, DVDs. Library, computer lab [sic].”

“Puppets, reading bags, books with illustrations [sic].”

Engaging in storytelling activities is a way to motivate even the most reluctant reader or writer. Storytelling is defined as relating a tale to one or more listeners through voice and gesture. If education is considered most effective when developed through social interaction and collaboration, it is understood that this pedagogical strategy capitalizes on students’ desire to speak and interact (BUSATTO, 2008).

For Oliveira (2017), storytelling is a fundamental method for sharing knowledge between people, as it allows participants to be transported to other places. Through the use of descriptive oral language, students are able to have an enhanced experience with literature, leading to new ways of seeing and perceiving the world.

Storytelling as a pedagogical strategy can strengthen reading comprehension, helping students to develop a sense of the story, which is fundamental to understanding the text and extracting meaning. In storytelling, the interaction is personal, engaging and immediate, characteristics that allow the audience’s attention to be captured. Students learn the social aspects of language through observation and participation (PROENÇA FILHO, 2007).

Students watch the storyteller use intonation and facial expressions to engage the audience and, when they retell these narratives, they have the opportunity to further develop their comprehension skills. According to Colli (2016), using the oral tradition of storytelling is a powerful strategy for defining patterns of meaning.

The pedagogical coordinator was asked if he encourages teachers to tell stories to their students in class, and he replied that he always does. Regarding the pedagogical resources that the pedagogical coordinator observes that teachers use to tell stories, he said that they use “Literary

clotheslines, story bags or just books [sic].”

According to Petit (2009), teachers who are regular readers are the most likely to use this strategy, while non-reading teachers seem less inclined to value interaction and the exchange of ideas about what is being read. In this sense, the teaching team should, in their planning meetings, encourage the use of this resource, especially among non-reading teachers.

In this sense, it is important to emphasize that the way in which teachers present reading to their students, the concrete actions they use to develop it, their own attitude towards books, consistency in carrying out activities that involve reading different types of texts and their own example and motivation, make students adopt their own view of reading, which can be positive or negative, depending mainly on the teaching model they are faced with (SOARES, 2007).

The teachers and pedagogical coordinator were asked if they had seen any specific methodology at school to help students with difficulties in developing language skills, reading and interpreting images or texts in children’s books or textbooks, and were asked to justify their response. Two teachers replied that no method has currently been developed, but they did not give any explanation as to why this was not the case. The others are presented below.

“No [sic].”

“No [sic].”

“Yes, there are two reading projects running at the school [sic].”

“Sometimes. It usually happens in school tutoring, but tutoring isn’t frequent [sic].”

“Yes, through new technologies, exploring the library and visiting the computer room [sic].”

“Two projects were carried out this year, one of them being the magic bookshelf, which encourages students to be authors. Another project was the reading and presentation of a text by the students at school break time [sic].”

“Not often [sic].”

It can be seen that the actions taken are fragmented, as the responses were not uniform, even though all the teachers work in the same

school and segment. It is known that reading and interpretation problems are common in the vast majority of classrooms and should therefore be part of the schools' joint actions.

Although most children learn to read reasonably well, Amarilha (2013) warns that there are still many whose future is compromised because they don't read well enough to meet the demands of a competitive, technology-driven society. In this context, schools must identify students in order to develop effective approaches, as well as enabling the professional development of teachers and the gaps that remain in their understanding of the mechanisms involved in the development of reading and writing. These are actions that involve parents, teachers, schools, communities, the media and government at all levels.

This situation must be taken into account in the teacher's pedagogical practice, and teachers must be instructed to take into account their students' tastes when thinking about actions to help these students, since the idea is that reading is a pleasurable moment, which is related to their interests, which causes satisfaction and responds to their own concerns, without neglecting the learning that is expected; In other words, the way in which the teacher carries out his or her pedagogical practice, the concrete actions he or she takes in the classroom, make the student construct his or her own conceptions of the process and development of reading (COSSON, 2009).

CONCLUSION

Activities that feed children's imagination and their ability to make believe promote creative and academic skills. Thus, storytelling and acting, mime, pantomime are among the most enjoyable activities for them.

When we tried to identify the methodologies used by the teachers, we found that they understand the importance of children's literature and that they use various resources for its development, being encouraged by the school's pedagogical team to use different strategies for the students' development.

The methodology cited by the teachers involves storytelling, puppet workshops, skits, performances, among others considered important for establishing content and disinhibiting the more shy. However, it was observed that the actions are fragmented, without a clear definition of the objectives to be achieved. At the end of this research and in view of the results obtained from the teachers and the pedagogical coordinator, it is recommended that teachers develop effective teaching strategies to train readers. To this end, it is very important that they pay attention to how they present reading to children, what strategies they use and how they can make it fun, engaging and meaningful.

It is important for the pedagogical coordination to provide teachers with collective moments to develop creative planning, to organize workshops, to guide the use of innovative methods and practices, to promote the use of educational tools and to monitor their use.

It can therefore be concluded that there is an understanding on the part of professionals that children's literature is an important element in the development of the learning process, as it stimulates motivation and strengthens reading comprehension. However, progress still needs to be made in the methodologies used in order to offer students opportunities to make sense of texts and understand the potential of each mode of communication, in order to make choices that allow them to create and understand messages more fully.

REFERENCES

- AMARILHA, M. Alice who didn't go to wonderland: educating to read fiction at school. São Paulo: Livraria da Física, 2013.
- BAKHTIN, M. Marxism and Philosophy of Language: Fundamental Problems of the Sociological Method in the Science of Language. São Paulo: Hucitec, 1999.
- BARDIN, L. Content analysis. São Paulo: Editions, 70, 2011.

- BUSATTO, C. Contar e encantar: pequenos segredos da narrativa. 5. ed. Petrópolis: Vozes, 2008.
- CAVALCANTI, J. Caminhos da literatura infantil e juvenil: dinâmicas e vivências na ação. São Paulo: Paulus, 2002.
- COLLI, R. A. Children's Literature in Early Childhood Education. 2016. 47f. Course Conclusion Paper (Graduation in Pedagogy) - State University of Londrina, Londrina, 2016.
- COSSON, R. Literary Literacy: theory and practice. São Paulo: Contexto, 2009.
- FERREIRA, M. O. V. Feminization and the "nature" of teaching work: a brief reflection on two stages. *Revista Retratos de la Escuela*, v. 9, n. 16, p. 153-166, 2015.
- HIRATA, G.; OLIVEIRA, J. B. A.; MEREB, T. M. Teachers: who they are, where they work, how much they earn. *Ensaio: aval pol publ Educ*, v. 27, n. 102, p. 179-203, 2019.
- HUNT, P. Criticism, theory and children's literature. Trad. Cid Knipel. São Paulo: Cosac Naify, 2010.
- MOURA, A. A. V.; MARTINS, L. R. Reading mediation: from the project to the classroom. In: BORTONI-RICARDO, S. M. et al. (Orgs.) *Leitura e Mediação Pedagógica*. São Paulo: Parábola, 2012.
- OLIVEIRA, R. M. Children's Literature: its importance in the literacy process and in the child's social development. *Revista Científica Multidisciplinar Núcleo do Conhecimento*, v. 13, n. 1, p. 375-394, 2017.
- PROENÇA FILHO, D. A linguagem literária. São Paulo: Ática, 2007.
- SOARES, M. The schooling of children's and young adult literature. In: EVANGELISTA, A. A. M.; BRANDÃO, H. M. B.; MACHADO, M. Z. V. (Orgs.). *Schooling literary reading*. Belo Horizonte: Autêntica, 2007.
- SOLÉ, I. *Reading Strategies*. 6. ed. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 1998.
- ZILBERMAN R.; LAJOLO, M. *A Formação da Leitura no Brasil*. São Paulo: Ática, 2005.